

HyDelta 4

WP2B – Purging – Optimal grid concept at 16 bar

D2b.1 Purging large diameters for industrial distribution grids

Status: final

Document summary

Corresponding author

Corresponding author	S.L.M. Lueb
Connected to	Kiwa Technology
Email address	sander.lueb@kiwa.com

Document history

Version	Date	Authors	Affiliated to	Summary of the revisions
1	9-1-26	Sander Lueb, Nico Hommels	Kiwa Technology	Draft with the overall structure of the report.
2	5-2-26	Sander Lueb, Nico Hommels	Kiwa Technology	Draft report with full elaboration.
3	23-2-26	Sander Lueb, Nico Hommels	Kiwa Technology	Processing of EAG responses.
4	6-3-26	Sander Lueb, Nico Hommels	Kiwa Technology	Processing of responses from the proofreader outside the EAG.
5	9-4-26	Sander Lueb, Nico Hommels	Kiwa Technology	Processing of responses Supervisory Group.

Distribution level

PU	Public	X
RE	Restricted to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project partners including the Expert Assessment Group External entities with whom a confidentiality agreement exists 	

Document review

Partner	Name
RENDO	Roy Scholten
Enexis	Herman Bodde
Firan	Erik-Jan Boonen
NBNL, Gasunie, Kiwa, DNV, TNO, NEC, Hanze	HyDelta Supervisory Group

Tag for website; Technology and Safety – Activities

Summary

As part of the national HyDelta research programme, a study was conducted into the purging of distribution pipelines with diameters larger than DN200.

The research described in this report forms part of HyDelta 4.0, work package 2 “Optimal grid concept at 16 bar”, and concerns sub-study WP2B: Purging of large diameters for industrial distribution gas grids.

Purging activities are applied to prevent the formation of flammable gas mixtures in pipelines during the introduction of hydrogen. At present, such purging activities mainly take place within pilot projects in the built environment and typically involve pipelines with diameters up to DN200.

When a pipeline is filled with air, it is common practice to first completely purge the pipeline with nitrogen in order to displace oxygen. Hydrogen is introduced only after sufficient inerting has been achieved. For this procedure, a recommended hydrogen purging speed of 1.0 m/s applies [1]. If a pipeline is already filled with natural gas, it can be purged directly with hydrogen, as this does not lead to the formation of flammable mixtures [2].

In the construction of industrial hydrogen distribution gas grids, pipeline diameters larger than DN200 may be applied. In such cases, the amount of nitrogen required for full inerting can become substantial. For this reason, this study investigated whether alternative purging techniques are available. In addition, field tests were carried out to determine whether purging with a nitrogen buffer (also referred to as pulse purging) can be used as an effective method to keep air and hydrogen separated during the purging process.

Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions are drawn:

Theoretical research

Several techniques can be considered to make a distribution pipeline hydrogen-carrying without the formation of flammable gas mixtures. From a practical perspective, the following techniques are considered the most applicable:

- completely purging with an inert gas (nitrogen or CO₂),
- completely purging using natural gas as an intermediate medium (air–natural gas–hydrogen),
- pulse (or slug) purging (buffer).

Depending on the grid configuration, one of these techniques may be more suitable than the other. Full purging is a technique with which grid operators are familiar.

Directly purging an air-filled pipe with hydrogen is a possibility that does not require nitrogen. The disadvantage of this is that flammable mixtures are formed. However, the question is to what extent it is realistic for these mixtures to ignite and what the consequences would be. It is advisable to conduct additional research into the possibilities of ignition and the effects of an unexpected ignition. Variables to be carried out in such an investigation include the hydrogen/air ratios in the gas, pipe length, diameter, and ignition sources.

For a complete overview of the various techniques, including techniques considered less suitable, see Chapter 3 and Attachment I.

Practical research

A DN400 pipe filled with nitrogen can be commissioned to carry hydrogen without stratification occurring. This has been demonstrated at flow velocities of 0.5 m/s and above.

Pulse purging proved to be an effective method for making a distribution grid hydrogen-carrying. Both the length of the nitrogen buffer and the purging speed are determining factors in preventing the formation of hydrogen–air mixtures. The length of the pulse (buffer) must be at least 100 metres, while the hydrogen start-up purging speed should be at least 1.0 m/s. At lower start-up purging speeds and/or shorter buffer lengths, hydrogen–air mixtures may form. This is caused by the lower density of hydrogen compared to nitrogen, which results in hydrogen tending to flow over the nitrogen buffer. Interruptions during the preparation of the nitrogen buffer have a detrimental effect on its effectiveness. In such situations, a buffer length of 100 metres is insufficient, and flammable mixtures may occur. Examples of interruptions are applying the buffer in two parts or a period of stagnation of the nitrogen buffer. Such interruptions may occur under practical conditions.

Branches connected to a main pipeline must be purged separately with nitrogen. When a nitrogen buffer is installed in the main pipeline, the air contained in a branch is not fully displaced. During subsequent hydrogen purging, this trapped air may enter the main pipeline, which can lead to the formation of flammable mixtures.

The presence of a bridge or a pipe line below ground level within a buffer does not cause any adverse effects. Due to the very slight differences in density between nitrogen and air, no interaction occurs at the interface between nitrogen and air. At the transition from nitrogen to hydrogen, however, interaction between the gases does occur, just as it does during regular purging. Following an upward flow in the pipe, the length of the hydrogen/nitrogen mixture decreases. Following a downward flow in the pipe, the length of the mixture increases. This more or less cancels each other out.

Recommendation for practical application

Based on the conducted research, the following recommendations are made regarding commissioning hydrogen large-diameter pipes (up to DN400) by means of pulse purging.

1. Maintain a minimum start-up purging speed of 1.0 m/s.
2. Apply a buffer length corresponding to 10% of the pipe length to be purged, with a minimum of 200 meters. The nitrogen buffer must be prepared without interruptions, and hydrogen purging must be started shortly thereafter. This buffer length is greater than the distance mentioned above. See Chapter 6 for an explanation of this additional safety margin.
3. Ensure that branch lines are free of air by purging them with nitrogen.
4. Apply a venting or flaring system equipped with a flame arrestor.
5. For the first hydrogen distribution gas grids and the application of pulse purging, provide monitoring points along the pipeline to follow the progress of the purging process. At a minimum, such a monitoring point should be installed at the end of the trace in order to verify that the purging process has been effective and that no flammable mixtures have formed. Where possible, it is recommended to have indicative knowledge of the applied nitrogen buffer length.
6. Share the experiences gained at 5 with the sector.

Contents

Document summary	2
Summary	3
Contents	5
1. Background and objective	7
1.1 General.....	7
1.2 Problem statement and background	7
1.3 Objective	7
2. Method.....	8
2.1 Theoretical research	8
2.2 Practical research – Pulse Purging	8
2.2.1 Measurements with bridge without branches.....	9
2.2.2 Measurements without bridge and without branches	10
2.2.3 Measurements without bridge and with branches	10
3. Results of the theoretical research	11
3.1 Most realistic options (Question 1)	11
3.1.1 The starting point for the considerations is a 20 km route.....	13
3.2 From natural gas to hydrogen	13
3.3 Displacement of air with hydrogen.....	13
3.4 Fully inerting the pipeline	14
3.4.1 Fully inerting pipeline (sections) with nitrogen (Question 2).....	14
3.4.2 Fully inerting pipeline (sections) with CO ₂	15
3.5 Pulse purging.....	16
3.6 Pigging (Question 3).....	16
3.6.1 PIG and service lines	17
3.7 Pressure swing and vacuum swing	18
3.7.1 Pressure Swing.....	18
3.7.2 Vacuum swing.....	19
4. Measurement results and findings of the practical research	21
4.1 Regular purging – with bridge.....	22
4.2 Purging with a 150-metre buffer – with bridge	22
4.3 Purging with a 50-metre buffer – with bridge	22
4.4 Purging with a 100-metre buffer – without bridge.....	23
4.5 Purging with 100-metre buffer 100 with interruptions – without bridge	23

4.6	Change in the length of the nitrogen/hydrogen mixture during purging.....	24
5.	Conclusions.....	26
5.1	Conclusions of the theoretical research	26
5.2	Overall conclusions of the practical research	26
6.	Recommendations.....	28
	References.....	30
	Attachments	31
I.	Overview of possible purging techniques	32
II.	Vacuum swing concentration and time progression.....	34
III.	Schematic representation of the test setup.....	36
IV.	Overview of measuring equipment used	38
V.	Photos of the test setup	39
VI.	Overview of measurements performed.....	45
VII.	Findings per measurement	46
VIII.	Explosion limits of nitrogen-hydrogen-air mixtures.....	67

1. Background and objective

1.1 General

This research was carried out within the framework of the national HyDelta research programme. This programme is aimed at the safe integration of hydrogen into the existing infrastructure for gas transport and gas distribution. Its objective is to remove barriers for innovative hydrogen projects. The complete research programme is divided into work packages. For an explanation of the various work packages, see www.hydelta.nl.

This report concerns the purging of distribution pipelines with a large diameter (DN300/DN400).

1.2 Problem statement and background

Regional gas distribution grid operators are making preparations for the reuse of existing natural gas grids to enable hydrogen distribution. In addition, preparations are being made for the construction of new hydrogen gas grids. Part of this concerns the purging of these gas grids (both new and existing).

Purging has been applied in various pilot projects in which an existing grid in the built environment was used as a hydrogen distribution grid. Now that an industrial application is becoming more concrete, involving the installation of pipelines with larger diameters, there is a need for insight into the purging of large-diameter hydrogen gas grids.

Based on previous conducted research, [1] it is known that hydrogen pipelines up to and including DN200 can be safely commissioned and decommissioned. Safe in this context means that a pipeline filled with air is first purged with nitrogen. This is done in order to keep hydrogen separated from air. In this way, no flammable mixtures are formed.

With larger diameters, it is not clear whether stratification occurs when nitrogen is displaced by hydrogen. In addition, fully purging the pipeline with nitrogen requires a large quantity of nitrogen.

1.3 Objective

The aim of this research is to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the most practical ways to purge hydrogen gas grids with a large diameter?
2. How does purging with nitrogen become a practically feasible method? How much nitrogen is required? Can this be supplied in an efficient manner? Is local production a possible solution?
3. What facilities are required to make pigging possible?
4. Can pulse purging with nitrogen be applied effectively?

The first three questions are answered on the basis of theoretical research. The fourth question is answered on the basis of practical research.

2. Method

This chapter indicates how the research questions were answered. The first three questions were answered based on theoretical research. The fourth research question has been answered on the basis of practical research.

2.1 Theoretical research

In answering research question 1, the research carried out within the framework of HyDelta 3 [3] was initially used. This research made use of the most recent literature. For answering question 2, it was investigated what the possibilities are at this moment for obtaining nitrogen at the relevant location. The answer to question 3 was based on the experiences with pigging in the transport network.

2.2 Practical research – Pulse Purging

The objective of the practical research is to determine whether pulse purging can be applied effectively. Based on the practical research, research question 4 is answered. The research was carried out using a test setup consisting of:

- PVC pipeline with a length of 195 meters with an outer diameter of 400 mm and an inner diameter of 378 mm, fitted with four bends.
- Venting via an open pipe with a nominal diameter of 125 mm.
- Bridge in the middle of the test pipeline (measurements 1 to 16).
- Branches with a diameter of 400 mm and a length of 10 meters at 45 m and 147 m (measurements 23 to 27).

See Attachment IV for a schematic representation of the test setup. It also shows the positioning of the oxygen and hydrogen sensors.

PVC will not be used for 16 bar distribution gas grids. This material was selected for the test setup because it is easy to install and allows the desired modifications to the test configuration (with or without bridge, with or without branches, installation of measuring points) to be implemented more easily. The internal diameter of the PVC pipeline corresponds to that of a steel pipeline with the same nominal diameter, which is a material that can be applied in practice. The wall roughness of steel is slightly higher than that of PVC. At low flow velocities (< 2 m/s), as applied during purging activities, wall roughness is of minor importance [4].

During purging activities on hydrogen gas grids, as carried out by a regional grid operator, a flare/venting system with a flame arrestor will be used at the point of exit. The application of such a system (with a hose with a diameter of 1 ^{1/4}”, DN32) causes a constriction in the outlet and consequently a pressure build-up in the pipe being purged. In the given test setup and with the chosen flow rates, this results in a final pressure build-up of approximately 100 mbar. The connected hydrogen detectors cannot withstand this pressure; therefore, a venting system with a larger diameter, without a flame arrestor, was chosen to keep the pressure build-up in the pipe to a minimum. For practical applications, it will be necessary to provide a venting/flare system with a flame arrestor capable of discharging the relevant capacity. The flare systems currently used by regional grid operators can discharge this flow rate.

2.2.1 Measurements with bridge without branches

In this configuration, the following aspects were investigated:

Regular purging (measurements 2 to 5)

These measurements were carried out to determine whether effective purging takes place (i.e. without stratification) when purging is performed in a regular manner. Regular purging means that the pipeline is first completely filled with nitrogen, after which the nitrogen is displaced by hydrogen. This procedure is applied during the commissioning of a hydrogen distribution grid. Subsequently, it was assessed whether decommissioning using nitrogen can also be carried out effectively. This was done by purging the hydrogen-filled pipeline with nitrogen.

Based on these tests, the length of the hydrogen/nitrogen mixture was also determined.

The filling with hydrogen was performed with a start-up purging speed of 0.8 m/s (duplicate measurement) and 0.3 m/s (duplicate measurement). The setting of the purge gas (hydrogen) was not changed during the measurements. As the pipeline becomes increasingly filled with hydrogen, the resistance of the medium to be displaced decreases, resulting in an increase in flow velocity.

The removal using nitrogen was performed with a nitrogen start-up purging speed of 0.7 m/s (for all four measurements). The setting of the purge gas (nitrogen) was not changed during the measurements. As the pipeline becomes increasingly filled with nitrogen, the resistance of the medium to be displaced increases, resulting in a decrease in flow velocity.

Note: Measurement 1 concerns a measurement during which the hydrogen supply was depleted during the test. Due to the observed disturbances, this measurement has nevertheless been included in this report.

Purging with a pulse (buffer) (measurements 6 to 16)

These measurements were carried out to determine whether purging with a pulse (buffer) can be performed effectively. In other words, whether hydrogen remains separated from air and whether the pipeline is completely filled with hydrogen at the end of the measurements. These measurements were performed with

- a 150 m nitrogen buffer and a hydrogen start-up purging speed of 0.3 m/s (triplicate measurement);
- a 150 m nitrogen buffer and a hydrogen start-up purging speed of 0.8 m/s (duplicate measurement);
- a 50 m nitrogen buffer and a hydrogen start-up purging speed of 0.3 m/s (triplicate measurement);
- a 50 m nitrogen buffer and a hydrogen start-up purging speed of 0.8 m/s (triplicate measurement).

During these measurements, the nitrogen buffer was introduced at a speed of approximately 0.2 m/s. As soon as a clear decrease in oxygen concentrations was observed at the respective distances (50 or 150 meters) at all three heights (high, middle and low), the nitrogen supply was stopped. Hydrogen and oxygen concentrations were measured at distances of 50 m, 100 m, and 150 m from the inlet. The hydrogen concentration in the discharge pipe was measured at a distance of 200 meters from the inlet. As soon as the concentration at this position reached 100%, the hydrogen supply was stopped.

At the end of these individual measurements, the hydrogen is removed by blowing air into the inlet of the test setup using an ATEX fan (Ramfan, type EF8002). The flow rate of this air stream is approximately 1,300 m³/h. This also applies to the measurements described below.

2.2.2 Measurements without bridge and without branches

Based on the findings of the measurements described in Section 2.2.1, it was decided to continue the measurements using a buffer length of 100 metres and a hydrogen start-up purging speed of 0.8 m/s. The bridge structure was placed flat on the ground, so that the test setup consisted of the same pipeline sections (including bends). The measurements were carried out without the bridge in order to obtain better insight into the transition zone of air/buffer/hydrogen. It is known that, in the ascending part of the bridge, hydrogen concentrations are distributed more homogeneously across the entire pipe cross-section. In other words, the gas concentrations at the high, middle and low positions are closer to each other.

To gain insight into the effect of possible interruptions during the installation of the nitrogen buffer, the following situations were measured:

- a 100-metre buffer followed shortly thereafter by the start of purging with hydrogen (measurements 17 and 18);
- preparation of a 100-metre buffer in two parts (measurements 19 and 20);
- preparation of a 100-metre buffer followed by a waiting period of 10 minutes (measurements 21 and 22).

In measurements 17 and 18, the buffer was prepared with a purging speed of 0.75 m/s, with the supply being stopped at the moment the oxygen concentrations at the high, middle and low positions dropped below 5% (the duration was approximately 120 seconds).

In measurements 19 and 20, the buffer was prepared with a purging speed of 0.75 m/s, with the nitrogen supply being opened twice for a period of 60 seconds. A waiting period of 10 minutes was applied between these injections.

In measurements 21 and 22, the buffer was prepared with purging speeds of 0.6 m/s and 0.4 m/s respectively, with the supply being stopped at the moment the oxygen concentrations at the high, middle and low positions dropped below 5%. After preparation of the buffer, a waiting period of 10 minutes was applied before purging with hydrogen was started.

2.2.3 Measurements without bridge and with branches

For the time being, it is assumed that regional grid operators will install a shut-off valve at each branch of the main pipeline (this does not concern a service pipeline). If such a branch crosses under a road, it may occur that the shut-off valve is located at a distance of 10 meters from the straight-ahead main pipeline. In order to determine the influence of the presence of air in a branch (with the shut-off valve closed), tests were carried out using a buffer and two branches. In this configuration, the effect of possible interruptions during the installation of the nitrogen buffer was also assessed. The following situations were measured:

- 100-meter buffer followed shortly thereafter by the start of purging with hydrogen (measurements 23 and 25);
- Preparation of a 100-metre buffer followed by a waiting period of 10 minutes (measurements 24 and 26);
- Preparation of a 100-meter buffer in two parts (measurement 27).

3. Results of the theoretical research

There are various methods available to commission a gas pipeline for hydrogen distribution. Within HyDelta 1 [2] and HyDelta 3 [3], extensive (literature) research was conducted into these various methods for converting a pipeline to hydrogen-carrying. These methods, along with several additional ones, are listed in Attachment I. Of all methods, four methods are considered the most practically applicable. Two other techniques are further explained in this chapter but are not considered viable.

The six described methods are part of the answers to the questions as formulated in Chapter 1.3. The response to question 1 is included in Section 3.1, the answer to question 2 in section 3, and question 3 is addressed in section 3.6.

3.1 Most realistic options (Question 1)

The most realistic (practically feasible) methods for purging large-diameter hydrogen gas grids are as follows:

- Direct displacement of natural gas with hydrogen, Section 3.2
- Direct displacement of air with hydrogen, Section 3.3
- Displacement of air by fully inerting the pipeline, followed by introduction of hydrogen Chapter 3.4
- Pulse (or slug) purging using a nitrogen buffer between air and hydrogen, Section 3.5

In addition, two supplementary methods were evaluated. These methods were assessed as less realistic or feasible compared to the four methods listed above. These are:

- Pigging, Section 3.6
- Pressure swing and Vacuum swing, Section 3.7

For the “pressure swing” method, a quantitative assessment was performed to demonstrate that more nitrogen is required compared to direct purging. For the “vacuum swing” method, calculations were carried out to determine how deep the vacuum must be in order to remain below the flammability limit under atmospheric conditions after mixing with air. This analysis serves as a supplement to earlier research [1] [3].

The purging methods described above, including the associated considerations, are summarised in Table 1 on the following page.

Table 1 Summary of assessed purging methods

Aspect under assessment	Evaluated purging methods						
	Displacement of natural gas with hydrogen	Displacement of air with hydrogen	Fully inerting the pipeline	Pulse purging	Pigging	Pressure swing	Vacuum swing
Formation of a flammable mixture	No	Yes	No	Configuration dependent	No	Yes	Yes
Known DSO technique	Yes	Yes	Yes	More or less	No	No	No
Applicability of the technique	Decreasing*	Good	Good**	Good**	Good***	Good**	Unknown
Estimated duration	Single purge	Single purge	Double purge	Inert buffer + single purge	Insertion / removal + a single purge	At least three purges	Depending on the size of the vacuum pump
Location	Flexible	Flexible	Flexible	Flexible	Fixed points	Flexible	Flexible
Required amount of inert gas	No	No	1.5 to 2.5 times the pipeline volume	10% of pipeline volume	No	More than 3× the pipeline volume	Depending on the depth of the vacuum

* Use and availability of natural gas may decrease in the future

** Gases can be readily supplied during planned works

*** If the facilities were installed during construction

3.1.1 The starting point for the considerations is a 20 km route.

The pipeline to be commissioned, within which the theoretical framework has been developed, comprises a route of up to 20 km DN400. This maximum length of 20 km has been identified by the EAG as the maximum section that can be commissioned in a single operation. In accordance with the Dutch standard NEN 7244-1, pipelines with a maximum operating pressure exceeding 200 mbar must be equipped with shut-off valves at a mutual distance of no more than 10 km. Regional distribution system operators often apply a distance of 5 kilometres. These lengths are typically purged per kilometer (sectioning by means of gas blowing). Based on this information, the framework considers pipeline sections of up to 1 kilometer, from 1 to 5 kilometres, and from 5 to 20 kilometres. This results in the purging volumes listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Some purging parameters of a DN400 pipeline

Pipeline route	Purge flow rate at 1 m/s [m ³ /h]	Volume of gas to be displaced [m ³]	Minimum purging time [min]
20 km DN400	440	2,450	340
5 km DN400	440	613	85
1 km DN400	440	122	17

3.2 From natural gas to hydrogen

A pipeline filled with natural gas can easily be converted to hydrogen. This has been investigated in HyDelta 1, report D1C.1 [2]. With this purging method, no flammable mixtures of natural gas and air or hydrogen and air are formed. During the purging, a flare installation is used to combust the flammable gas removed from the pipeline.

Another approach is to use natural gas as an intermediate medium to make a pipeline hydrogen-carrying. This entails that an air-filled pipeline is first filled with natural gas and subsequently with hydrogen. These two separate purging steps result in a hydrogen-carrying pipeline starting from air. An advantage of this approach is that displacing air with natural gas is a widely applied practice among grid operators. The availability of natural gas via a nearby distribution pipeline may be an advantage compared to nitrogen, which must be supplied via trailers or cylinder packages.

For a new pipeline, however, it may be undesirable to use natural gas as an intermediate medium for converting the route to hydrogen-carrying for several reasons. Reasons for not doing so include:

- additional environmental impact (greenhouse gas),
- contamination of the pipe,
- decreasing availability of natural gas.

3.3 Displacement of air with hydrogen

In this method, air is directly displaced by hydrogen. This is a method comparable to current practices during the commissioning and decommissioning of a natural gas pipeline, where air is directly displaced by natural gas or vice versa. During this procedure, a flammable mixture is formed in the gas pipeline. At present, this is considered an unacceptable method for purging with hydrogen due to the different risks involved compared to natural gas. These risks differ, for example, because of the wider flammability limits of hydrogen compared to natural gas. Nevertheless, the practice of displacing air with a flammable gas is well known among regional grid operators, the required facilities are available, and it requires only limited additional training or education for technicians.

Studies conducted by Steer Energy [5], [6] do not rule out direct hydrogen purging. This research combines theoretical approaches to purging rates in conjunction with pipe diameters and practical tests on PE pipes. Conditions for applying direct purging include the use of a flare system with a flame arrestor and minimum purging rates. Additionally, further research is proposed in the aforementioned report. This includes, among other things, studying the ignition behavior of mixtures with different compositions of hydrogen and air. Other variables in this regard are pipe length, diameter and ignition sources.

3.4 Fully inerting the pipeline

The use of an inert gas to inert a gas-carrying pipeline is a commonly applied method to prevent the formation of flammable mixtures of hydrogen and air within a pipeline. This method can be applied both during commissioning and decommissioning of a pipeline. Research carried out by Kiwa [1] and research by the American Gas Association (AGA) [7] shows that the most effective purging velocity is 1 metre per second. The most obvious inert gases for this purpose are nitrogen, argon and carbon dioxide (CO₂). In the context of inerting gas (distribution) pipelines, nitrogen and CO₂ are logical choices due to their relatively low costs. For these gases, it is generally necessary to use two to three times the internal volume of the pipeline in order to achieve full inerting. Values ranging from 1.5 to 2.5 times the pipeline volume are reported in the literature cited.

Further explanation of the practical aspects and considerations related to purging with nitrogen or CO₂ is provided in Sections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2.

3.4.1 Fully inerting pipeline (sections) with nitrogen (Question 2)

Fully inerting large-diameter pipelines over long distances requires a substantial amount of nitrogen. The required quantity of nitrogen and the means by which it can be made available at the site are described in the following paragraphs. This is followed by an explanation of nitrogen availability from suppliers. Based on these considerations, Table 3 can be compiled. In this table, the internal volume of the pipeline sections has been multiplied by three in order to ensure that a sufficient quantity of inert gas is available for the purging operation.

Table 3 Supplying nitrogen using different methods

Pipeline route	Estimated volume [m ³]	Supply method	Required quantity
20 km DN400	7,350	Liquid	1 to 2 liquid deliveries*
20 km DN400	7,350	Tube Trailer	2 to 3 deliveries*
20 km DN400	7,350	Trailer with bundles	6 to 7 trailer deliveries
20 km DN400	7,350	Local Production	1 trailer
5 km DN400	1,840	Bundles	1 to 2 trailers with bundles
5 km DN400	1,840	Local production	1 trailer
1 km DN400	370	Bundles	3 to 4 bundles

* depending on trailer availability

Supply of the required quantity of nitrogen

Broadly speaking, there are two methods for supplying nitrogen at the location where it is required: transportation of nitrogen by road or local production.

Nitrogen can be supplied by:

- a trailer with liquid nitrogen including a vaporiser
- a tube trailer with gaseous nitrogen
- a trailer fully loaded with nitrogen bundles
- individual delivery of nitrogen bundles

Transport

A delivery of liquid nitrogen comprises approximately 4,800 m³(s) to 13,000 m³(s) depending on the available cryogenic trailer [8]. A trailer fully loaded with nitrogen bundles contains approximately 1,200 m³(s) of nitrogen [9]. For this reason, the use of bundles is not practical for purging large volumes. The most practical method for supplying large quantities of nitrogen is therefore the use of liquid nitrogen

For purging a sectioned part of a pipeline, the use of individual bundles may be sufficient. A standard bundle consisting of 12 cylinders contains approximately 115 m³(s) of nitrogen. For an ideal purging operation of a 1-kilometre section, three to four bundles may be sufficient. When purging using bundles, attention must be paid to the connection method. This can be achieved by means of a semi-automatic pressure reduction station, which provides flexibility for the distribution system operator.

Local Gas Production

A second method of supply is the local production of nitrogen using a nitrogen generator. In this case, nitrogen and oxygen are locally separated from ambient air. The nitrogen is introduced into the pipeline, while the oxygen is released back into the atmosphere. The technology required for this is available and can be built semi-permanently on a trailer or mobile unit. Nitrogen generators suitable for mounting on trailers typically have a maximum capacity of approximately 1,000 m³(n)/h. With this capacity, a 5 km DN400 pipeline section can be purged within approximately 2 hours.

Availability of the required quantity of nitrogen

Purchasing nitrogen is an adequate solution for planned activities. However, in the event of emergencies where nitrogen must be available quickly, procurement can become a delaying factor that is not acceptable. Several approaches can be considered to address this issue. In the event of an emergency in which a limited section of the route can be isolated, nitrogen bundles may be sufficient. Nitrogen bundles are generally kept in stock, are easy to transport, and can typically be delivered to site within approximately three hours under emergency conditions [8]. When larger quantities of nitrogen must be available immediately on demand, a 24/7 availability contract can be concluded with a gas supplier. Under such an arrangement, one or more nitrogen trailers are kept on standby in exchange for a fee. This is an expensive solution, as payment is required for availability regardless of whether the nitrogen is actually used, and is therefore not considered an efficient option. An alternative consideration is the use of an in-house mobile nitrogen generator. Such a unit can be available within the organisation on a 24/7 basis and, depending on storage locations, can be deployed relatively quickly on site.

3.4.2 Fully inerting pipeline (sections) with CO₂

A potential bottleneck for purging with carbon dioxide is the availability of the gas at the location of the pipeline to be purged. As with nitrogen, two key factors are relevant: the method of supply and availability.

Supply

CO₂ can be purchased in a manner similar to nitrogen, and the same supply-related considerations apply. Local production, however, would differ significantly and is not considered a viable option. CO₂ could theoretically be produced in the form of flue gases through the combustion of fuels such as diesel. The combustion process results in additional emissions of CO₂, CO, NO_x and particulate matter to the environment. Furthermore, diesel combustion is typically carried out with an excess of air in order to prevent soot formation. As a result, oxygen is nevertheless introduced into the pipeline route, which is precisely what should be avoided.

In the future, CO₂ may potentially become available via pipeline transport. There is a growing number of initiatives related to CCS (Carbon Capture and Storage). Should a pipeline grid for CO₂ transport emerge, similar to the existing infrastructure for natural gas, it may be possible that a CO₂ pipeline is available nearby from which CO₂ can be fed into the pipeline to be purged. A point of criticism regarding this approach is that CO₂ is more environmentally harmful than nitrogen.

Availability

The same considerations apply as those described for nitrogen with regard to procurement and 24/7 availability; reference is made to Section 3.4.1

3.5 Pulse purging

Pulse purging is a process in which air in a pipeline is displaced by hydrogen, with a nitrogen buffer positioned between the two. Figure 1 provides a visual representation of this concept. The hydrogen pushes the nitrogen forward, which in turn displaces the air ahead of it. This concept is briefly described and defined in ASME B31.12-2023 [10]. An advantage of this method is that it is not necessary to fill the entire pipeline with nitrogen, resulting in time savings and reduced nitrogen consumption. The technical feasibility of this process has been investigated experimentally within this study (see, among others, Sections 2.2, 4 and 5.2).

Figure 1 Visual representation of pulse purging, showing a nitrogen buffer between air and hydrogen

3.6 Pigging (Question 3)

This method makes use of a physical barrier between two gases or media by means of a PIG. A PIG (pipeline inspection gauge) is used to inspect, clean or facilitate the purging of a pipeline. An extensive installation is required to insert and retrieve the PIG from the pipeline, consisting of a launch and a receiving station [11]. For this method, bends, branches and valves within the route must be suitable for pigging in order to prevent the PIG from becoming stuck within the pipeline [9].

Figure 2 A PIG forming a barrier between hydrogen and air to prevent the formation of flammable mixtures

The PIG is used as a physical barrier between hydrogen and air (see Figure 2). The red hydrogen gas is separated from the blue air by the green plug. As a result, no mixing occurs between hydrogen and air. Due to the pressure difference between the supplied hydrogen (higher pressure) and the outgoing air (lower pressure), the PIG moves through the pipeline. This method could be a workable solution for long pipeline routes that are yet to be developed. For routes shorter than 5 kilometres, branched routes, and retrofit situations (reuse of existing natural gas pipelines), this method is not considered feasible. In addition, service lines cannot be purged using a PIG. Various approaches can be applied to address this issue.

3.6.1 PIG and service lines

A PIG is an ideal solution for long pipeline routes where this functionality has been incorporated during the design and construction phases. With careful design, branched pipeline gas grids can also be purged, provided that the internal diameters are identical. A condition is that a receiving and/or launching station is installed at the end of each pipeline. A remaining challenge is how to deal with pipelines of smaller diameter, such as service lines. By definition, these branches are not purged by the PIG. This issue can be addressed in several ways. Four options are outlined below. Option three is considered the most practical. This approach is currently also applied in the natural gas grid. It should be noted, however, that additional research is required to gain greater insight into the risks associated with hydrogen–air mixtures.

1. Purging the service line with an inert gas from the branch point towards the customer
2. Purging the service line with an inert gas from the customer towards the branch point
3. Purging the service line with hydrogen from the branch point towards the customer
4. Purging the service line with hydrogen from the customer towards the branch point

1. Purging the service line with an inert gas from the branch point towards the customer

This purging operation must take place while the PIG process is also ongoing. By supplying nitrogen at the branch point of a service line and discharging it at the customer end, the service line is filled with nitrogen and air is displaced. This eliminates the possibility of forming a flammable mixture. Once the PIG has passed the branch point, the nitrogen supply can be stopped and replaced by hydrogen supplied from the main pipeline. When hydrogen is detected at the customer end, the purging operation is complete. For this approach, a purging facility would have to be installed at every branch point. Installation is costly, and purging each individual branch line is time-consuming. In addition, nitrogen must be made available. For these reasons, this option is not considered a workable solution. For safety reasons, the temporary installation of a flare system at each customer location may be considered. This measure may be somewhat excessive and is not applied in the natural gas grid. Nevertheless, the supplied hydrogen must be discharged and monitored in a safe manner. The use of an anti-static hose may be a workable solution. This approach creates a safe working method.

2. Purging the service line with an inert gas from the customer towards the branch point

This option requires a supply installation to be set up at each customer location. Whether this is desirable is questionable. The installation purges an inert gas towards the main pipeline. Once the PIG has passed the branch point, the supply of inert gas can be stopped. Subsequently, the service line must be purged with hydrogen from the main pipeline towards the customer. For safety reasons, the temporary installation of a flare system at each customer location can again be considered. This measure may be excessive and is not applied in the natural gas grid. Nevertheless, the supplied hydrogen must be safely discharged and monitored. The use of an anti-static hose may be a workable solution. This approach creates a safe working method.

3. Purging the service line with hydrogen from the branch point towards the customer

In this approach, the main pipeline is first made hydrogen-carrying using the PIG method. Subsequently, the service lines are purged with hydrogen via the customer installation. When a service line that is initially filled with air is purged in this manner, a flammable mixture is formed. The magnitude of the associated risk is currently unknown. Factors influencing the risk include the presence of ignition sources, the size of the flammable mixture and the duration for which the flammable mixture is present [5]. Additional research is required to enable a more conclusive assessment. This research is in line with studies on the working method as referenced in Section 3.3: Displacement of air with hydrogen. An advantage of this approach is that it represents a well-known working method that is also applied in the current natural gas grid.

4. Purging the service line with hydrogen from the customer towards the branch point

For this working method, a hydrogen supply must be installed at the customer location in order to purge hydrogen towards the main pipeline. When a service line that is initially filled with air is purged in this manner, a flammable mixture is formed. An additional aspect compared to option 3 is whether hydrogen is purged towards a main pipeline filled with air or a main pipeline filled with hydrogen. In both cases, air from the service line is displaced into the main pipeline. The starting point is to directly introduce the hydrogen purge from the customer into the main pipeline. Discharging at the branch point is not considered, as this would require the installation of additional purging points at each branch. The remaining question is therefore whether hydrogen is supplied to an air-filled main pipeline, or whether air from the service line is introduced into a hydrogen-filled main pipeline. In both cases, a detailed assessment is required of the size of the potential flammable mixtures and the associated risks. The magnitude of these risks is currently unknown. Influencing factors include ignition sources, the size of the flammable mixture and the duration for which the flammable mixture is present. Further research is required to draw firm conclusions. This research is in line with investigations of the working method as referenced in Section 3.3, Displacement of air with hydrogen.

In all cases, the gas composition in the main pipeline must also be monitored. This can be carried out at the end point of the main pipeline, where a venting and/or flaring facility will be available. The reason for monitoring is that impurities (such as nitrogen and air) may enter the main pipeline from the service lines.

3.7 Pressure swing and vacuum swing

Based on a more detailed assessment of the pressure swing and vacuum swing purging processes, the conclusion is that these methods do not constitute a better approach than purging with nitrogen. In both vacuum swing and pressure swing processes, a flammable mixture is formed when a flammable gas is used to bring the pipeline up to pressure. When an inert gas is used for pressurisation, it is preferable to apply direct purging with nitrogen instead. In addition, the application of vacuum swing requires further investigation with regard to the suitability of fittings, components and connections present in the grid for vacuum conditions. The following sections provide a more detailed explanation of the reasons for not applying these methods.

3.7.1 Pressure Swing

A pressure swing involves the controlled pressurisation of a pipeline with a gas, followed by controlled depressurisation. The objective is to dilute and replace the gas present in the pipeline by increasing the pressure and introducing the gas that is ultimately intended to be used. To achieve this, an inert gas is generally used to pressurise the pipeline in order to dilute the air. By using an inert gas, the formation of a flammable mixture is avoided. This working method introduces

challenges similar to those discussed in Section 3.1.3 with regard to the supply of inert gases. Depending on the final pressure, a pressure swing must be performed multiple times [12], potentially requiring more inert gas than effectively purging a pipeline. Depending on the selected pressure, the depressurisation rate and the level of turbulence within the pipeline, branch lines may be purged less effectively with this method than the main pipeline in the direction of the venting point. The pressure swing method is well suited for purging closed vessels, where gas cannot flow freely but is confined, and is therefore not a technique specifically intended for application in pipeline systems. Within the distribution sector, the pressure swing methodology could be applied in situations involving the installation of stopple equipment or equipment related to inflatable gasstoppers.

To gain insight into how many pressure swing cycles are required to exceed the upper flammability limit, several simplified calculations have been performed. The results are presented in Table 4. In this calculation example, no account is taken of the compressibility factor of the gas. Furthermore, it is assumed that the pipeline can be fully depressurised within an acceptable period of time, and any residual pressure in the pipeline is not included in the calculation of concentration.

Table 4 Pressure swing with different final pressures

Pressure swing of a 20 km DN 400 section; 2,450 m ³					
Initial pressure	Final pressure	Number of swings	Required amount of hydrogen [m ³]	Multiple of pipeline volume	Hydrogen concentration in air*
0 bar(g)	1 bar(g)	3	10,106	4.1	81%
0 bar(g)	2 bar(g)	2	11,433	4.6	89%
0 bar(g)	3.5 bar(g)	1	8,575	3.5	78%

* The upper flammability limit for hydrogen is 75%

3.7.2 Vacuum swing

A vacuum swing involves bringing a pipeline route under negative pressure and subsequently bringing the route back up to pressure using a (inert) gas. This process ensures that air is removed from all locations within the pipeline. The pipeline can then be returned to atmospheric pressure by introducing an inert gas or a flammable gas. The choice of gas depends on the level of vacuum that can be achieved in the pipeline. The greater the vacuum that can be created, the more air is removed from the pipeline. With a lower level of vacuum, multiple swings between vacuum and atmospheric pressure using an inert gas will be required to reduce the air concentration in the pipeline to a sufficiently low level before a flammable gas can be introduced. Another possibility is to increase the pressure of the pipeline directly from a vacuum condition to a higher operating pressure. This results in greater dilution of the air present in the pipeline.

A possible advantage of vacuum swing compared to pressure swing is that, with vacuum swing, the service lines are also cleared of gas. During a pressure swing, it is possible that the gas present in the service line does not mix sufficiently, resulting in a less effective pressure swing. As a result, air may remain behind and become trapped in the service line. By evacuating the pipeline using vacuum, air is also removed from the service line, after which the negative pressure in the service line is restored with an inert gas or directly with hydrogen.

In addition, careful consideration must be given to the fittings and materials used within the grid. Fittings that are designed for higher pressures are not necessarily suitable for vacuum conditions. A continuing point of attention is that when the negative pressure is eliminated by introducing a flammable gas, a flammable front will always form between the air still present in the pipeline and

the introduced flammable gas. No statement is made as to whether the duration and size of the flammable mixture are acceptable. By means of an approach based on the given pipeline route, a calculation example will be used to provide insight into the expected concentrations and duration of a flammable mixture. In this example, pressure is restored by introducing hydrogen.

A summary of the approach is given in Table 5. This is based on a filling rate of 440 m³/h of hydrogen. Using this filling rate, three situations have been calculated. Situation I has a starting point of a negative pressure of 100 mbar (0.9 bar(a)), situation II has a starting point of a negative pressure of 500 mbar (0.5 bar(a)), and situation III a negative pressure of 750 mbar (0.25 bar(a)). Values for situations Ia, IIa and IIIa represent concentrations and times required to pressurise to 1 bar. Values for situations Ib, IIb and IIIb indicate the time elapsed before the concentration in the pipeline exceeds the upper flammability limit. In this approach, no account has been taken of where in the pipeline a flammable mixture is formed or how large this front may be. The calculated concentrations assume homogeneous mixing and that hydrogen follows the ideal gas law. When approximating a 20-kilometre route, this is not realistic when pressures above 10 bar are also considered. However, it does provide an indication of the time required to exceed the upper flammability limit over the entire pipeline.

Table 5 Route concentrations at a hydrogen purging flow rate of 440 m³/h

Situation	Ia	IIa	IIIa	Ib	IIb	IIIb
Negative pressure [bar(a)]	0.9	0.5	0.25	0.9	0.5	0.25
Final pressure [bar(a)]	1.0	1.0	1.0	4.0	2.2	1.0
% hydrogen in air	10%	50%	75%	>75%	>75%	>75%
Elapsed time [min]	34	168	251	900	500	251

Attachment II provides the corresponding graphs showing the pressure and concentration trends.

4. Measurement results and findings of the practical research

This chapter presents the main results and findings of the experiments. The graphical representations are included in Attachment VII. There are two important conditions for successful purging during the commissioning of a hydrogen pipeline. These are:

- achieving a fully hydrogen-carrying pipeline (100% H₂ at all positions);
- preventing mixtures of hydrogen and air.

Measurements 2 through 5, 7, 8, 10, 17, and 18 as listed in the table below meet these two conditions (shaded in dark green).

Table 6 Overview of measurements performed in the different configurations and the result of the purging

Measurement	Buffer	Bridge	Branches	Initial purging velocity H ₂ (m/s)	Pipe fully hydrogen-carrying	Mixture H ₂ /O ₂	Flammable mixture
1	no	yes	no	0.7	no	yes	yes
2	no	yes	no	0.8	yes	no	no
3	no	yes	no	0.8	yes	no	no
4	no	yes	no	0.3	yes	no	no
5	no	yes	no	0.3	yes	no	no
6	150 m	yes	no	0.3	yes	yes	no
7	150 m	yes	no	0.3	yes	no	no
8	150 m	yes	no	0.8	Yes	no	no
9	150 m	yes	no	0.3	yes	yes	no
10	150 m	yes	no	0.8	yes	no	no
11	50 m	yes	no	0.3	yes	yes	yes
12	50 m	yes	no	0.3	yes	yes	yes
13	50 m	yes	no	0.3	no, stopped purging too soon	yes	yes
14	50 m	yes	no	0.8	yes	yes	no
15	50 m	yes	no	0.8	yes	yes	no
16	50 m	yes	no	0.8	yes	yes	no
17	100 m	no	no	0.8	yes	just not	no
18	100 m	no	no	0.8	yes	just not	no
19	100 m in 2 sections	no	no	0.9	yes	just	yes
20	100 m in 2 sections	no	no	0.8	yes	just	yes
21	100 m - 10 min w.	no	no	0.8	yes	just	yes
22	100 m - 10 min w.	no	no	0.7	yes	yes	yes
23	100 m	no	yes	0.8	no	yes	yes
24	100 m - 10 min w.	no	yes	0.8	yes	yes	yes
25	100 m	no	yes	0.8	yes	yes	yes
26	100 m - 10 min w.	no	yes	0.9	yes	yes	yes
27	100 m in 2 sections	no	yes	0.8	yes	yes	yes

Purging using a buffer proves to be successfully applicable when:

- the buffer has a minimum length of 100 metres and is introduced in one step
- the minimum initial purging velocity is 0.8 m/s;
- purging with hydrogen is started immediately after introducing the buffer;
- the pipeline section to be purged does not contain branches filled with air.

In paragraphs 4.1 to 4.5 results for each measurement are explained in more detail.

4.1 Regular purging – with bridge

Measurements 2 and 3

With an initial purging velocity of 0.8 m/s, hydrogen is able to completely displace the nitrogen. With an initial purging velocity of 0.7 m/s, nitrogen is able to completely displace the hydrogen. At distances of 50 and 150 metres, a small amount of oxygen is present at the positions at the bottom of the pipeline. This may be caused by a residual amount of air in a branch cap. The oxygen concentration is sufficiently low (< 4.2%) such that the mixture is not flammable. For an explanation of the flammability of hydrogen–nitrogen–oxygen mixtures, reference is made to see Attachment VIII.

Measurements 4 and 5

With an initial purging velocity of 0.3 m/s, hydrogen is able to completely displace the nitrogen. With an initial purging velocity of 0.7 m/s, nitrogen is able to completely displace the hydrogen. At a distance of 150 metres, a small amount of oxygen is present at the position at the bottom of the pipeline. This may be caused by a residual amount of air in a branch cap. The oxygen concentration is sufficiently low (< 4.2%) such that the mixture is not flammable.

Measurements 1 through 5

At the measuring point before the bridge (50 m), the hydrogen concentrations at the top, middle and bottom differ during the purging periods. At the bridge, the hydrogen concentration is more homogeneously mixed and there is almost no difference between the concentrations at the top, middle and bottom. After the bridge (150 m), the hydrogen concentrations at the top, middle and bottom diverge again.

4.2 Purging with a 150-metre buffer – with bridge

Measurements 6 and 9 (initial purging velocity 0.3 m/s)

At the measuring point at 150 metres, a mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed. The oxygen concentration is sufficiently low (< 4.2%) such that the mixture is not flammable.

Measurement 7 (initial purging velocity 0.3 m/s)

At the measuring point at 150 metres, no mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed.

Measurements 8 and 10 (initial purging velocity 0.8 m/s)

At the measuring point at 150 metres, no mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed. At the higher purging velocity, the time between the absence of oxygen and the presence of hydrogen is greater compared to the measurements with the lower purging velocity.

4.3 Purging with a 50-metre buffer – with bridge

Measurements 11 and 12 (initial purging velocity 0.3 m/s)

At a distance of 100 and 150 meters, a flammable mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed. This mixture is present in the pipe for approximately 10 minutes.

Measurement 13 (initial purging velocity 0.3 m/s)

At a distance of 150 metres, a flammable mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed. This mixture is present in the pipeline for approximately 5 minutes. The length of the mixture in measurement 13 is somewhat shorter because the buffer is slightly longer than in measurements 11 and 12. This can be observed from the stronger decrease in the oxygen concentration at measuring point 1.

Measurement and 14, 15 and 16 (initial purging velocity 0.8 m/s)

At a distance of 150 metres, a mixture of oxygen and air is formed. However, this is not a flammable mixture because the oxygen concentration is lower than 4.2%. The higher velocity compared to measurements 11 through 13 ensures that the buffer is stretched less.

Based on the initial findings and discussions with the EAG, it was decided to continue the measurements with a buffer length of 100 metres in combination with the highest initial purging velocity. As a result, measuring position 1 was moved from 50 metres to 195 metres.

4.4 Purging with a 100-metre buffer – without bridge

Without branches – measurements 17 and 18

At distances of 100 and 150 metres, no mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are formed. The oxygen concentration has already decreased to 0% for some time before the hydrogen concentration begins to increase. At a distance of 195 metres, **just no mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed**; at the moment the oxygen concentration has dropped to 0%, the hydrogen concentration starts to increase. Based on the analysis in Section 4.6, it is stated that the length of the nitrogen/hydrogen mixture remains approximately the same when comparing the positions 150 metres and 195 metres.

With branches - measurements 23 and 25

At all distances in the pipeline (100, 150 and 195 metres), **mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are formed**. During the purging process, the hydrogen concentration begins to increase while oxygen is still present in the pipeline. This oxygen originates from both branches. When introducing the 100-metre buffer, not all air is displaced from the first branch (45 m). During purging with hydrogen, hydrogen enters the full length of both branches. This was established by disconnecting the oxygen sensor at the highest point at the end of the branches and measuring the hydrogen concentration at that location.

4.5 Purging with 100-metre buffer 100 with interruptions – without bridge

Purging with an interrupted buffer adversely affects the ability to maintain the buffer length. This also applies when branches containing air are present. Both effects lead to the formation of a hydrogen–air mixture.

Without branches – buffer applied in two parts – measurement 19 and 20

At distances of 100 and 150 metres, no mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are formed. The oxygen concentration drops to 0%, after which the hydrogen concentration starts to increase shortly thereafter. At a distance of 195 metres, however, a mixture of oxygen and hydrogen **is formed**. Shortly before the oxygen concentration reaches 0%, the hydrogen concentration has already begun to rise.

Without branches – wait 10 minutes after buffer application – measurements 21 and 22

At distances of 100 and 150 metres, no mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are observed. The oxygen concentration drops to 0%, followed shortly by an increase in hydrogen concentration. At a distance of 195 metres, a mixture of oxygen and hydrogen **is formed**. By the time the oxygen concentration has reached 0%, the hydrogen concentration has already increased. In measurement 22, the overlap between the decreasing oxygen concentration and the increasing hydrogen concentration is slightly larger than in measurement 21.

With branches – buffer applied in two parts – measurement 27

Mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen **are formed** at all distances within the pipeline (100, 150 and 195 metres). During the purging process, the hydrogen concentration begins to increase while oxygen is still present in the pipeline. This oxygen originates from both branches.

When installing the 100-metre buffer in two parts, not all air is expelled from the first branch (45 m). During hydrogen purging, hydrogen is therefore present along the entire length of both branches.

With branches – 10 minutes delay after buffer application – measurements 24 and 26

Measurement 24: At distances of 150 and 195 m, mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are formed. This most likely also occurs at a distance of 100 m; however, this cannot be determined with certainty, as the oxygen sensor failed during the measurement.

Measurement 26: At all distances within the pipeline (100, 150 and 195 m), mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen **are formed**. At a distance of 100 m, the oxygen concentration is below 4.2%, meaning no flammable mixture is present. At distances of 150 and 195 m, flammable mixtures are present.

During hydrogen purging, hydrogen is present along the entire length of both branches. This was determined by disconnecting the oxygen sensor at the highest point at the end of the branches and measuring the hydrogen concentration at that location.

4.6 Change in the length of the nitrogen/hydrogen mixture during purging

When purging a pipeline that is (partially) filled with nitrogen, the introduced hydrogen will partially displace and flow over the nitrogen. As a result, the originally injected buffer spreads over a greater length of the pipeline, forming a nitrogen–hydrogen mixture over an extended section.

For the measurements performed, the development of the mixture length during the purging process was determined. This was done to assess whether the chosen buffer length remains effective for pipeline lengths exceeding the tested 200 m.

For each distance configuration (50, 100, 150 or 100, 150 and 195 m), the length of the nitrogen–hydrogen mixture was determined. This was achieved by recording the time between the initial rise in hydrogen concentration and the moment when a hydrogen concentration of 99% was reached at each measurement level (high, middle and low). The average purging velocity for this period was derived. The measured time (s), multiplied by the purging velocity (m/s), results in the calculated length of the mixture.

As an example of this methodology, the results of Measurement 2 are presented below.

Table 7 Example for the determination of the nitrogen/hydrogen mixture – measurement 2

	MP1 (50 m)			MP2 (100 m)			MP3 (150m)		
	h	m	l	h	m	l	h	m	l
Time of first hydrogen increase	15:22:08	15:22:18	15:22:28	15:22:38	15:22:48	15:22:48	15:23:28	15:23:28	15:23:38
Time at 99% hydrogen	15:24:18	15:25:58	15:26:18	15:26:18	15:25:48	15:25:48	15:26:08	15:26:28	15:26:28
Time difference per measuring position between first increase and 99% hydrogen	00:02:10	00:03:40	00:03:50	00:03:40	00:03:00	00:03:00	00:02:40	00:03:00	00:02:50
Mixing time [minutes]	00:04:10			00:03:10			00:03:00		
Average purging velocity during this period [m/s]	1,28			1,53			1,68		
Mixing time [seconds]	250			190			180		
Mixing length [m]	319			292			302		

During purging, the hydrogen flow velocity increases slightly. As the amount of “heavy” nitrogen in the pipeline gradually decreases, the resistance encountered by the introduced hydrogen is reduced. For this measurement, however, this increase in velocity has little effect on the overall length of the mixture.

In the table below, the mixture length for all measurements is presented. The values have been rounded to tens of metres, as the hydrogen concentrations were recorded at 10-second intervals. As a result, the moment at which a specific concentration is reached may in practice have been observed up to 10 seconds later. Consequently, the actual duration for which the mixture is present may be shorter, resulting in a deviation of approximately 3 to 18 metres (10 seconds multiplied by the local purging velocity).

Table 8 The length and velocity of the flowing mixture during the purging process

Measure- ment	Starting speed H ₂ purging (m/s)	What does the length of the N ₂ /H ₂ mixture do during the purging process? (150 vs 50 or 195 vs 150)	Length of mixture at various distances in the pipe				flow rate of mixture (m/s)			
			50 m	100 m	150 m	195 m	50 m	100 m	150 m	195 m
1	0.7	<i>unable to determine</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	400	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	<i>n.d.</i>	0.6	<0.3	<i>n.d.</i>
2	0.8	remains approximately the same	320	290	300	<i>n.d.</i>	1.3	1.5	1.7	<i>n.d.</i>
3	0.8	becomes smaller	400	300	340	<i>n.d.</i>	1.4	1.5	1.6	<i>n.d.</i>
4	0.3	is getting bigger	410	320	500	<i>n.d.</i>	0.5	0.5	0.6	<i>n.d.</i>
5	0.3	is getting bigger	380	300	460	<i>n.d.</i>	0.6	0.5	0.7	<i>n.d.</i>
6	0.3	remains the same	410	310	410	<i>n.d.</i>	0.6	0.6	0.8	<i>n.d.</i>
7	0.3	is getting bigger	410	320	450	<i>n.d.</i>	0.6	0.6	0.7	<i>n.d.</i>
8	0.8	remains the same	330	320	330	<i>n.d.</i>	1.4	1.5	1.6	<i>n.d.</i>
9	0.3	is getting bigger	320	270	460	<i>n.d.</i>	0.3	0.3	0.4	<i>n.d.</i>
10	0.8	becomes smaller	380	300	340	<i>n.d.</i>	1.3	1.3	1.4	<i>n.d.</i>
11	0.3	is getting bigger	300	260	410	<i>n.d.</i>	0.3	0.3	0.3	<i>n.d.</i>
12	0.3	is getting bigger	340	270	440	<i>n.d.</i>	0.3	0.3	0.3	<i>n.d.</i>
13	0.3	is getting bigger	320	290	370	<i>n.d.</i>	0.3	0.3	0.2	<i>n.d.</i>
14	0.8	remains the same	400	400	400	<i>n.d.</i>	1.4	1.5	1.6	<i>n.d.</i>
15	0.8	remains the same	430	340	430	<i>n.d.</i>	1.0	1.0	1.1	<i>n.d.</i>
16	0.8	becomes smaller	390	310	350	<i>n.d.</i>	1.4	1.4	1.5	<i>n.d.</i>
17	0.8	remains approximately the same	<i>n.d.</i>	350	380	400	<i>n.d.</i>	1.0	1.0	1.1
18	0.8	remains approximately the same	<i>n.d.</i>	330	460	450	<i>n.d.</i>	1.0	0.9	0.9
19	0.9	remains approximately the same	<i>n.d.</i>	270	330	310	<i>n.d.</i>	1.2	1.4	1.5
20	0.8	remains approximately the same	<i>n.d.</i>	270	360	370	<i>n.d.</i>	1.0	1.0	1.1
21	0.8	remains the same	<i>n.d.</i>	300	420	420	<i>n.d.</i>	0.9	0.9	0.9
22	0.7	remains the same	<i>n.d.</i>	270	340	340	<i>n.d.</i>	1.3	1.4	1.5
23	0.8	becomes smaller	<i>n.d.</i>	380	520	480	<i>n.d.</i>	1.2	1.1	1.1
24	0.8	becomes smaller	<i>n.d.</i>	390	510	480	<i>n.d.</i>	1.2	1.1	1.1
25	0.8	becomes smaller	<i>n.d.</i>	320	400	340	<i>n.d.</i>	1.5	1.7	1.8
26	0.9	becomes smaller	<i>n.d.</i>	310	420	360	<i>n.d.</i>	1.5	1.8	1.8
7	0.8	remains approximately the same	<i>n.d.</i>	300	350	330	<i>n.d.</i>	1.6	1.8	1.8

5. Conclusions

5.1 Conclusions of the theoretical research

The three most practical and safest methods for converting large-diameter gas grids to hydrogen service are:

- Direct displacement of the existing natural gas with hydrogen;
- Displacement of air by fully inerting the pipeline, followed by purging with hydrogen;
- Pulse purging using a nitrogen buffer between air and hydrogen.

5.2 Overall conclusions of the practical research

Pulse purging is a feasible method to keep hydrogen and air separated, requiring a significantly smaller amount of nitrogen compared to conventional nitrogen purging of pipelines.

Based on the experiments performed, the following conclusions were drawn:

Conventional purging (measurements 2 to 5)

Large-diameter pipelines (up to 400 mm) that are completely filled with nitrogen can be fully converted to hydrogen service when a purging velocity of 0.5 m/s or higher is applied.

Large-diameter pipelines (up to 400 mm) that are completely filled with hydrogen can be made hydrogen-free when a purging velocity of 0.5 m/s of nitrogen is applied.

With constant settings for the supplied gas, the hydrogen purging velocity increases during the conversion to hydrogen service. Conversely, during nitrogen purging, the nitrogen purging velocity decreases over the course of the process.

Purging with a 150-metre buffer (measurements 6 to 10)

With a buffer length of 150 metres and a low purging velocity (0.3 m/s), mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are formed; however, no flammable mixtures occur.

With a buffer length of 150 metres and a higher purging velocity (0.8 m/s), no mixtures of hydrogen and air are formed.

Purging with a 50-metre buffer (measurements 11 through 16)

With a buffer length of 50 metres and a low hydrogen purging velocity, flammable mixtures are formed.

With a buffer length of 50 metres and a high hydrogen purging velocity, mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen are formed; however, these mixtures are just below the flammability limit.

Purging with a 100-metre buffer (measurements 17 to 22)

Purging with a buffer length of 100 metres is just sufficient to prevent the formation of oxygen–hydrogen mixtures. Applying the buffer in two stages or introducing a standstill period results in the formation of flammable mixtures of oxygen and hydrogen.

Purging and the effect of branches (measurements 23 to 27)

When injecting a 100-m nitrogen buffer, air remains trapped in the branch located within the buffer section. During purging with hydrogen, air from both branches enters the main pipeline. At the same time, hydrogen also enters both branches during hydrogen purging.

Length of hydrogen/nitrogen mixture during all measurements

Based on Table 8, it is concluded that at a higher purging velocity (0.8 m/s or higher), the length of the mixture at the end of the pipeline does not increase further. The formation of the mixture is therefore stabilized. It is expected that the mixture length will remain stable even for longer pipeline sections than the 200 m used in the test setup. Whether or not a flammable mixture is formed depends on the initially selected buffer length.

Length of hydrogen/nitrogen mixture during measurements with a bridge (measurements 2 to 16)

At the bridge, the mixture lengths decrease compared to the mixture lengths measured at the preceding measurement location. After passing the bridge, the mixture lengths increase again. This effect occurs at both low and high purging velocities.

In seven of the eight measurements, a low purging velocity results in an increase in mixture length when comparing the mixture length at 150 m with that at 50 m from the start of the pipeline.

In all seven measurements, a high purging velocity does not result in an increase in mixture length when comparing the mixture length at 150 m with that at 50 m from the start of the pipeline.

Length of hydrogen/nitrogen mixture during measurements without a bridge and without branches (measurements 17 to 22)

When comparing the measurement points at 100 m and 150 m, the length of the hydrogen–nitrogen mixture increases during the purging process. Further downstream, at the end of the pipeline (195 m), the mixture length appears to have remained stable relative to the mixture length at 150 m. In other words, for a longer pipeline section to be purged, the mixture length will not increase further.

Length of hydrogen/nitrogen/air mixture during measurements without a bridge and with branches (measurements 23 to 27)

During measurements with branches, some mixing takes place between nitrogen from the buffer and air originating from the branches. Once hydrogen is introduced, extensive mixing between hydrogen and air from the branches also occurs. The resulting mixture therefore consists of nitrogen from the buffer, air from the branches and hydrogen.

When comparing the measurement points at 100 m and 150 m, the length of the hydrogen–nitrogen mixture increases during the purging process. Further downstream, at the end of the pipeline (195 m), the mixture length appears to have decreased compared to the mixture length measured at 150 m.

6. Recommendations

Based on the theoretical study

Directly purging an air-filled pipeline with hydrogen may also be a feasible and safe method. To gain more insight into this, additional research is required. This research should consist of, among other things, practical tests involving the ignition of flammable mixtures with varying compositions and volumes in pipelines with different diameters and lengths. During these tests, the gas/air mixture should be discharged via a flare installation equipped with a flame arrester. Preferably, the influence of air present in service lines should also be taken into account in this research.

Based on the practical research

Based on the study performed, the following recommendations are made for converting large-diameter pipelines (up to DN400) to hydrogen service by means of pulsed purging:

1. Apply a minimum initial purging velocity of 1 m/s.
2. Apply a buffer length corresponding to 10% of the pipeline length to be purged, with a minimum of 200 metres. The nitrogen buffer should be installed without interruptions, and hydrogen purging should commence shortly thereafter.
3. Ensure that branches are made free of air by purging them with nitrogen
4. Apply a flame arrester in the venting/flare installation.
5. For the first hydrogen distribution gas grids and the application of pulse purging, provide measurement points along the pipeline in order to monitor the progress of the purging process. Such a measurement point should at least be located at the end of the route. At this point, it should be determined whether the purging has been effective without the formation of flammable mixtures. In this context, it is advisable to have indicative knowledge of the size of the nitrogen buffer applied.
6. Share the experiences gained at 5 with the sector.

Ad 1.

During the purging process, the resistance of the medium to be displaced (air and the nitrogen buffer) decreases as the proportion of hydrogen increases. Without changes to the flow control, this will result in an increase in velocity and a reduction in the time required to complete the purging process.

Ad 2.

In the study, a buffer length of 100 metres at a purging velocity of 0.8 m/s proved sufficient to keep air and hydrogen separated. This applied to a test setup with a length of 200 metres. As pipeline sections to be purged in practice will be longer, a safety factor of 2 or higher is applied when selecting the buffer length. For example:

- For a pipeline section of 5 kilometres, the recommended buffer length is 500 metres (recommendation: 10%).
- For a pipeline section of 1.5 kilometres, the recommended buffer length is 200 metres (recommended minimum of 200 m).

Ad 3.

For the purging of a branch, several options are available. The air can be displaced in the direction of the main pipeline, but also in the direction of the branch. Once the branch is filled with nitrogen, it is expected that the nitrogen will remain present in the branch for some time (hours/days), as the density of air and nitrogen is approximately equal. The only way by which air from the main pipeline can re-enter the branch is by diffusion. This is a slow process.

Ad 4.

Between the individual measurements, the pipeline was made free of hydrogen by purging with air. During this process, flammable mixtures were, of course, formed. In the given test setup and with the associated supervision, this did not pose an objection. During the experiments performed, no spontaneous ignition occurred.

For actual commissioning activities, a flame arrester is prescribed in order to prevent flame flashback in the event of an unintended ignition near the outlet. This is despite the premise that, when applying pulsed purging, no flammable hydrogen/air mixtures are formed.

References

- [1] Kiwa Technology, "Spoelen van waterstofleidingen_GT-200289," 2021.
- [2] Kiwa Technology, "HyDelta D1C.1 Spoelen van aardgasleidingen met waterstof," 2021.
- [3] Kiwa Technology, "HyDelta 3 - D5A2 Spoelen van gasnetten, onderzoek naar alternatieven voor het spoelen met stikstof," 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/15011297>.
- [4] Kiwa Technology, "Spoelen van aardgasleidingen-GT200075," 2020.
- [5] Steer Energy, "HyPurge - Direct Purging of Networks to Hydrogen for H100 Fife," 2022.
- [6] S. Energy, "HyPurge Safe Tooling," 2023.
- [7] American Gas Association, "Purging Principles and Practice," 2001.
- [8] *Westfalen Gassen*. [Interview]. 15 01 2026.
- [9] Alliander, "Memo 028 Inertiseren en Spoelen HD".
- [10] ASME, "ASME B31.12_2023 Hydrogen Piping and Pipelines," 2023.
- [11] DNV, "D5.2 - Rapport over veilig afsluiten en evacueren van hogedruk waterstofpijpleidingen en -installaties voor onderhoudsdoeleinden," 2023.
- [12] NEN, "NPR-CEN/TR 15281 Potentiële plaatsen waar explosiegevaar kan heersen - Explosiepreventie en -bescherming - Leidraad voor inertisering ter voorkoming van ontploffingen," NEN, 2022.
- [13] V. Schroeder, "Calculation of flammability and lower flammability limits of gas mixtures for classification purposes," BAM, 2016.

Attachments

I. Overview of possible purging techniques

Converting pipeline to hydrogen service	Transition from-to	Described in;	Formation of flammable mixture	Advantage	Disadvantage
Gas purging – complete displacement	Air - Hydrogen	[3]/ [5]up to D = 250mm, length 40 meters) / [6](up to D = 250m)	Yes	no inert gas required	Formation of flammable mixture - HyPurgeSafeTooling and suitability up to a diameter of 63 mm. HyPurgeSafeTooling states that additional work is required for diameters larger than 63 mm.
Gas purging – complete displacement	Air - Nitrogen - Hydrogen	[1]	no	no flammable mixture	Large amount of N ₂ required.
Gas purging – complete displacement	Air - CO ₂ - Hydrogen	-	no	no flammable mixture, fairly easy to make with a heating device	Large amount of CO ₂ required; flue gases introduce moisture into the pipeline.
Gas purging – complete displacement	Air - Natural Gas - Hydrogen	[2]	no	no flammable mixture	Large amount of natural gas required.
Gas purging – complete displacement	Air - other inert gas - Hydrogen	[9]	no	no flammable mixture	Large amount of inert gas required.
Pigs	Air-Pig- Hydrogen	[3]/ [7]/[1]	no	No flammable mixture No additional gases required	Launching installation required – more complex – requires more handling actions and is therefore more hazardous.
Pigs	Air-Pig- Nitrogen-Pig- Hydrogen	[3]	no		Launching installation required – more complex – requires more handling actions and is therefore more hazardous.
Pulse purging	Air - buffer inert gas - Hydrogen	[3]	no	Limited amount of inert gas required	Uncertainty regarding the potential formation of a flammable mixtures.

Continue on the next page.

Converting pipeline to hydrogen service	Transition from-to	Described in;	Formation of flammable mixture	Advantage	Disadvantage
Vacuuming	Air - vacuum - hydrogen	[3]/[1]	unknown	no inert gas needed	Ingress of air depending on fittings and components. Unknown technique; can the pipeline withstand this underpressure? (1 bar underpressure)
Pressure variations (pressure swing)	Air-Nitrogen-Hydrogen or Air-Hydrogen	[3]/[12]	no	limited benefits	Branches are not purged. For large diameters, a large amount of nitrogen or other inert gas is required.
Gas blowing / inserting inflatable ball and propelling by gas pressure	Air - Hydrogen	-	no	No inert gas needed	Unknown technique. Removal/receiving installation required (variant of pigging).
Steam purging	Air – Steam – Hydrogen	[7]	unknown	Heat helps clean the pipes	Moisture remains in the pipeline and must subsequently be removed using an inert and dry gas such as nitrogen.
Inert gas generator	Air – Inert gas – hydrogen	[7]	no	no flammable mixture - inert gas to be produced on site	Purchase and maintenance of equipment.
Diesel exhaust gases	Air – flue gases – hydrogen	[7]	no	no flammable mixture - inert gas to be produced on site	CO formation and soot in case of incomplete combustion, or oxygen present in the pipeline when excess air is used for efficient combustion.
Water	Air – water – hydrogen	[7]	no	unknown	Moisture remains in the pipeline and must subsequently be removed using an inert and dry gas such as nitrogen.

II. Vacuum swing concentration and time progression

Situation I

Concentration profile for a pipeline section with a volume of 2450 m³. After creating an underpressure down to 0.9 bar(a), the pipeline is pressurised by filling it with hydrogen.

Situation II

Concentration profile for a pipeline section with a volume of 2450 m³. After creating an underpressure down to 0.5 bar(a), the pipeline is pressurised by filling it with hydrogen.

Situation III

Concentration profile for a pipeline section with a volume of 2450 m³. After creating an underpressure down to 0.25 bar(a), the pipeline is pressurised by filling it with hydrogen.

III. Schematic representation of the test setup

A detailed overview of the execution per measurement point is included on the following page.

Figure 3 Detail of measurement positions per measurement point

IV. Overview of measuring equipment used

Description	Manufacturer and type	Serial no.	Kiwa no.
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010032RNS	114633
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010034RNS	114634
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010045RN	114635
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010044RN	114637
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010033RN	114638
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010042RN	114639
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010049RN	114640
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	9Y3010050RN	114641
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	4X9010057RN	115396
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	4X9010055RN	115397
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	579020009RN	115671
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP-1000	579020017RN	115674
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254125	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254146	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254170	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254172	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254181	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254192	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254198	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254201	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254202	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254228	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254278	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254284	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254289	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254301	-
Oxygen detector	PyroScience FDO2	25254304	-
Gas meter (mass flow meter)	Bronkhorst F-106CI-AGD-01-V	M25211133A	-
Pressure gauge	Digitron B2022P	5107199449	112066

V. Photos of the test setup

Figure 4 and Figure 5 The piping before the bridge and the bridge

Figure 6 The downstream pipeline towards the venting pipe.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 The header with the hydrogen and nitrogen supply and the mass flow meter (yellow arrow).

Figure 9 and Figure 10 The fan that was placed at the inlet to make the pipe free of hydrogen (measurements 6 and higher)

Figure 11 and Figure 12 Nitrogen or hydrogen inlet and the capped branch at 45 m (measurements 1–22)

Figure 13 and Figure 14 The (capped) branch at 147 m and the detectors at measurement position 3 (150 m); sampling to the hydrogen meter via the oxygen sensor.

Figure 15 The venting pipe at the end of the measurement pipeline

Figure 16 and Figure 17 View of the test setup from the bridge (left towards the inlet, right towards the outlet)

Figure 18 The horizontal bridge structure for measurements 17 to 27

Figure 19 and Figure 20 The branch connections at 45 m and 147 m from the inlet (measurements 23–27)

Figure 21 The position of the measuring sensors for measuring oxygen concentrations at the branches.

VI. Overview of measurements performed

Measurement	Measurement date	Buffer	Bridge	Branches
1	27/08/2025	no	yes	no
2	27/08/2025	no	yes	no
3	27/08/2025	no	yes	no
4	28/08/2025	no	yes	no
5	28/08/2025	no	yes	no
6	28/08/2025	150 m	yes	no
7	28/08/2025	150 m	yes	no
8	29/08/2025	150 m	yes	no
9	29/08/2025	150 m	yes	no
10	29/08/2025	150 m	yes	no
11	29/08/2025	50 m	yes	no
12	29/08/2025	50 m	yes	no
13	01/09/2025	50 m	yes	no
14	01/09/2025	50 m	yes	no
15	01/09/2025	50 m	yes	no
16	01/09/2025	50 m	yes	no
17	02/09/2025	100 m	no	no
18	02/09/2025	100 m	no	no
19	02/09/2025	100 m in 2 parts	no	no
20	02/09/2025	100 m in 2 parts	no	no
21	02/09/2025	100 m - 10 min waiting	no	no
22	02/09/2025	100 m - 10 min waiting	no	no
23	03/09/2025	100 m	no	yes
24	03/09/2025	100 m - 10 min waiting	no	yes
25	03/09/2025	100 m	no	yes
26	03/09/2025	100 m - 10 min waiting	no	yes
27	03/09/2025	100 m in 2 parts	no	yes

VII. Findings per measurement

Meas. No. 1; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.7 m/s – Initial nitrogen purging velocity = 0.7 m/s
Configuration; with bridge – no branches – conventional purging

During the measurement, it appeared that the hydrogen supply package was depleted. The purging velocity dropped below 0.3 m/s, while the hydrogen concentration at the end of the pipeline had not yet reached 100%. This result shows that monitoring and maintaining the minimum purging velocity during the purging process is important for effective purging.

In the graph above, the result of the hydrogen measurement at “measuring point 1 – low” is missing. The corresponding meter showed a pump failure. The increase in oxygen concentration at “measuring point 1 – low” is caused by the same pump failure in the hydrogen meter. The gas extracted by the hydrogen meters passes through the oxygen sensors.

No. 2 & 3; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s – Initial nitrogen purging velocity = 0.7 m/s
 Configuration; with bridge – no branches – conventional purging

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

No. 4 & 5; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.3 m/s – Initial nitrogen purging velocity = 0.7 m/s
Configuration; with bridge – no branches – conventional purging

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 6; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.3 m/s – Hydrogen-free operation using a fan
Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 150-metre buffer

The oxygen measurement at measurement point 1 was unavailable between 13:19 and 14:31. After that, the oxygen concentrations were 0% (until 14:52).

Below, the same graph is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. A mixture of oxygen and hydrogen does just occur at measuring point 3 (150 metres, low). This is not a flammable mixture, as the oxygen concentration is < 4.2%. The oxygen concentration decreased to values below 0.5%, and shortly thereafter, the hydrogen concentration started to increase.

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurements 7 & 9; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.3 m/s - Dehydrogenation with fan Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 150 metre buffer

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 8; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 150 metre buffer

Below, the same graph is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. No mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration decreased to 0%, and the hydrogen concentration only started to increase approximately 1 minute later.

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 10; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 150 metre buffer

Below, the same graph is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. No mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration decreased to 0%, and the hydrogen concentration only started to increase approximately 1 minute later.

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 11 & 12; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.3 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
 Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 50 metre buffer

Below, the same graph as above is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. A mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentrations are higher than 4.2% at the moment the hydrogen concentration increases, resulting in a flammable mixture.

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 12; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.3 m/s - Dehydrogenation with fan Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 50 metre buffer

Measurement 13; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.2 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 50 metre buffer

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 14; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
 Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 50 metre buffer

Below, the same graph as above is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. A mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration is lower than 4.2% at the moment the hydrogen concentration increases, therefore no flammable mixture is formed.

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 15 & 16; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
 Configuration; with bridge – no branches – 50 metre buffer

Point 1 = 50 metres / Point 2 = 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 17; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
Configuration; without bridge – no branches – 100 metre buffer

Below, the same graph as above is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. No mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration decreased to 0% at the moment the hydrogen concentration increased. On the following page, the graph is shown with only the result for measurement point 1 (195 metres).

Point 1 = 195 metres / Point 2 – 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Below, the same graph as the overall graph of measurement 17 is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 1. **Just no** mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (195 metres). The oxygen concentration decreased to 0%, and immediately thereafter the hydrogen concentration increases.

Measurement 18; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – no branches – 100 metre buffer

Point 1 = 195 metres / Point 2 – 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 19; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.9 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
 Configuration; without bridge – no branches – 100 metre buffer in two parts

Below, the same graph as above is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. Just no mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration decreased to 0%, and immediately thereafter the hydrogen concentration increases. On the following page, the graph is shown with only the result for measuring point 1 (195 metres).

Point 1 = 195 metres / Point 2 – 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Below, the same graph as the overall graph of measurement 19 is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 1. A mixture of oxygen and hydrogen **is just** formed at measuring point 1 (195 metres). The oxygen concentration has not yet decreased to 0%, while the hydrogen concentration increases rapidly. This mixture is flammable, as the oxygen concentration is higher than 4.2%.

Measurement 20; Initial hydrogen purging velocity= 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – no branches – 100 metre buffer in two parts

Point 1 = 195 metres / Point 2 – 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 21; Initial hydrogen purging velocity= 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – no branches – 100 metre buffer and 10 min. waiting

Measurement 22; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.7 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – no branches – 100 metre buffer and 10 min. waiting

Point 1 = 195 metres / Point 2 – 100 metres / Point 3 = 150 metres

Measurement 23; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s – Hydrogen removal with fan
Configuration; without bridge – with branches – 100 metre buffer

The oxygen sensors at measurement point 4 were out of operation up to 10:11.

Below, the same graph as above is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. A flammable mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration decreases to almost 0%, but subsequently increases again to values above 4.2%. This is caused by air that was still present in the branch. On the following page, the graph is shown with only the result for measuring point 1 (195 metres).

Point 1 = 195 m / Point 2 = 100 m / Point 3 = 150 m / Point 4 = branch 45 m / Point 5 = branch 147 m

Below, the same graph as the overall graph of measurement 23 is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 1. A mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 1 (195 metres). The oxygen concentration has not yet decreased to 0%, while the hydrogen concentration increases rapidly. This mixture is flammable, as the oxygen concentration is higher than 4.2%. Subsequently, an oxygen concentration remains detectable at this position for a prolonged period; this will be supplied from the branches.

Measurement 25; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan
Configuration; without bridge – with branches – 100 metre buffer

During the disconnection of the O₂ sensor at measuring point 4 – high, the connection with the data logging system was lost. The sensor was disconnected to determine whether hydrogen was detectable at this position.

Point 1 = 195 m / Point 2 = 100 m / Point 3 = 150 m / Point 4 = branch 45 m / Point 5 = branch 147 m

Measurement 24; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s – Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – but branches – 100 metre buffer and 10 min. waiting

Below, the same graph as above is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 3. A flammable mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 3 (150 metres). The oxygen concentration decreases to almost 0%, but subsequently (at the bottom of the pipeline) increases again to values above 4.2%. This is caused by air that was still present in the branch. On the following page, the graph is shown with only the result for measuring point 1 (195 metres).

Point 1 = 195 m / Point 2 = 100 m / Point 3 = 150 m / Point 4 = branch 45 m / Point 5 = branch 147 m

Below, the same graph as the overall graph of measurement 24 is shown, but only with the concentrations at measuring point 1. A mixture of oxygen and hydrogen is formed at measuring point 1 (195 metres). The oxygen concentration has not yet decreased to 0%, while the hydrogen concentration increases rapidly. This mixture is flammable, as the oxygen concentration is higher than 4.2%. Subsequently, an oxygen concentration remains detectable at this position for a prolonged period; this will be supplied from the branches.

Measurement 26; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.9 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – but branches – 100 metre buffer and 10 min. waiting

During the disconnection of the O₂ sensor at measuring point 4 – high, the connection with the data-logging system was lost. The sensor was disconnected to determine whether hydrogen was detectable at this position.

Point 1 = 195 m / Point 2 = 100 m / Point 3 = 150 m / Point 4 = branch 45 m / Point 5 = branch 147 m

Measurement 27; Initial hydrogen purging velocity = 0.8 m/s - Hydrogen removal with fan Configuration; without bridge – but with branches – 100-metre buffer in two parts

During the disconnection of the O₂ sensor at measuring point 4 – high and measuring point 5 – high, the connection with the data-logging system was lost. These sensors were disconnected to determine whether hydrogen was detectable at these positions.

Point 1 = 195 m / Point 2 = 100 m / Point 3 = 150 m / Point 4 = branch 45 m / Point 5 = branch 147 m

VIII. Explosion limits of nitrogen-hydrogen-air mixtures

The figure below (excluding the green strip) is taken from [13], and is also included and explained in [1], .

From the figure above, it can for example be derived that a mixture of 20% hydrogen and 80% nitrogen is not flammable.

From the same figure it can also be derived that hydrogen–nitrogen–air mixtures with less than 20% air are not flammable. A mixture containing 20% air results in an oxygen percentage of 4.2%. A hydrogen–nitrogen–oxygen mixture with an oxygen concentration lower than 4.2% is therefore not flammable.